

ANESTHETIC PROTECTION DURING CARDIAC SURGERY WITH ARTIFICIAL CIRCULATION AT CHILDREN

¹Satvaldiyeva E.S., ²Sayramov I.Kh., ³Tuychiyev D.B.

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237721>

Abstract. It is important to suggest that till today there is no unambiguous opinion in the literature on the possibility of using sevoflurane and dexmedetomidine in open heart surgery in young children, which necessitates the development of an optimal model of anesthetic protection in cardiac anesthesiology for this category of patients. The object of the study were young children from 1 to 5 years old (n=60) with various congenital heart defects who underwent cardiac surgery with artificial circulation. The study group of 30 patients in which the effectiveness and safety of anesthesia with the combined use of dexmedetomidine were studied. The control group consisted of 30 children with classical, standard anesthetic protection under conditions of propofol, fentanyl and sevoflurane. The functions of the main life-support organs were studied: hemodynamics and tissue perfusion (electrocardiography, pulse oximetry), ventilation (capnography), gas exchange (CBS and blood gases), BIS monitoring; blood stress hormones (cortisol, glucose, lactate). According to the results of the study, it can suggest the stabilization of the main parameters of hemodynamics and respiration, which confirms the adequacy of anesthetic protection in patients of group 1. Thus, the mentioned method provides safe anesthesia, which is extremely important for postoperative mobilization and normalization of the patient after radical surgical interventions.

Keywords: children, cardiac surgery, anesthesia, BISS.

Introduction. What is more important for young children with congenital heart disease, the problems associated with high surgical and anesthetic risk on the one hand and adequate protection of the body from severe surgical trauma on the other hand remain relevant [4.12]. These circumstances determine the need to optimize anesthetic protection methods. Till today, there is no clear opinion in the literature on the possibility of using sevoflurane and dexmedetomidine in open-heart surgery in young children, which necessitates the development of an optimal model of anesthetic protection in cardiac anesthesiology for this category of patients [9.13]. Currently, cardiac surgery is recognized as an effective method for treating congenital heart defects in children, which has led to an increase in the duration and quality of their life. To a large extent, this has become possible due to the higher accuracy of preoperative diagnostics, optimization of patient preparation, improvement of surgical technique and artificial blood circulation methods achieved in recent decades.

In this regard, the priority area of research is the optimization of anesthetic management and intensive care of cardiac surgery patients, especially young children [Bokeria L.I.A., 2002; Laussen P.S., et al., 2003], [Kozlov I.A., et al., 2001]. Moreover, cardiac surgery in children is often performed under non-standard physiological conditions that are rarely encountered in other areas of clinical medicine. Examples include hypothermia up to 15 - 18 ° C, acute hemodilution by more than 50% of the extracellular fluid volume, complete circulatory arrest lasting up to 1 hour.

It is known to everyone that the ability to maintain and manage the patient's condition under these extreme conditions is a necessary professional quality of a pediatric cardiac anesthesiologist.

As in other areas of medicine, the use of modern technologies requires a thorough knowledge of their physiological effects. Of primary importance for a pediatric cardiac anesthesiologist is the information obtained from studies performed on children with CHD in real conditions of intensive care units and operating rooms [W.L. Greeley Professor, Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA]. The achievements of modern medical technologies are so great that they require a radical restructuring of all activities by the physician. Good treatment results, which were achieved already at the dawn of the development of pediatric cardiac surgery, essentially opened a new era in the treatment of CHD and stimulated the development and symbiosis of such specialists as pediatric cardiologists and cardiac surgeons.

Surprisingly, as a result of their cooperation, significant progress was achieved in the diagnosis and surgical treatment of CHD. As a consequence, specialists such as pediatric cardiac anesthesiologists emerged, whose areas of expertise include the pathophysiology of congenital heart disease, the diagnostic procedures and surgical interventions used to treat it, as well as pediatric and cardiovascular anesthesiology and intensive care. Today, pediatric cardiac anesthesiology continues to attract us as an exciting and technically advanced subspecialty based on physiological principles.

It is not a secret that the problem of perioperative cardio protection, especially under conditions of artificial circulation, is no less important [Kozlov I.A., Klipa T.V. 2017]. Today, the understanding of the pathophysiology and prevention of ischemia-reperfusion injury to the myocardium of the operated heart has expanded [Hausenloy D.J. et al, 2011; Grocott H.P. et al, 2011]. The issues of additional pharmacological cardio protection are discussed [Vinten-Johansen J., Thourani V.H., 2000]. In this regard, there has been an increased interest of clinicians in the α_2 -adrenergic receptor (α_2 -AR) agonist dexmedetomidine [Kozlov I.A., 2014], which is widely used both for sedation and as an organ protector and adjuvant in various operations [Soliman R., Zahri G. 2016; Brandão P.G. et al, 2016].

Despite sufficient experience in the use of dexmedetomidine in adult patients, the number of similar publications in children is limited, especially in cardiac surgery practice [van Hoorn CE et al, 2021; Welch TP et al, 2021; Curley MA et.al. 2015; Ji SH et al, 2022].

Thus, for young children with CHD, problems associated, on the one hand, with a high surgical and anesthetic risk, and on the other, with adequate protection of the body from severe surgical trauma, remain relevant. Currently, most anesthesiologists use dexmedetomidine in pediatrics for premedication, sedation and prevention of agitation, delirium in the intensive care unit.

Definitely, large intercontinental differences in the use of dexmedetomidine require consensus and training worldwide on its optimal use in children [van Hoorn CE et al. Off-label use of dexmedetomidine in paediatric anaesthesiology: an international survey of 791 (paediatric) anaesthesiologists. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2021 Apr;77(4):625-635.]

The objective of the study: to improve surgical outcomes in young children with congenital heart defects by optimizing anesthetic protection using dexmedetomidine with fentanyl and low-flow sevoflurane inhalation.

Materials and methods of the study. The object of the study were young children from 1 to 5 years old (n-30) with various congenital heart defects, who underwent cardiac surgery with

artificial circulation. The control group consisted of 30 children with classical, standard anesthetic protection under propofol, fentanyl and sevoflurane.

The groups were homogeneous in age, of primary and concomitant pathology, type and duration of surgical interventions. The functions of the main life support organs were studied: hemodynamics and tissue perfusion (electrocardiography, pulse oximetry), ventilation (capnography), gas exchange (CBS and blood gases), BIS monitoring; blood stress hormones (cortisol, glucose, lactate). Laboratory methods: some homeostasis parameters, parameters of liver and kidney functional activity (ALT, AST, bilirubin, total protein, urea, creatinine). Patients were recruited in the pediatric cardiac surgery department of Fergana Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center, equipped with a modern monitoring system, anesthesia and respiratory equipment and a laboratory.

The criteria for excluding children from the research work were

- Intolerance to the drugs used in the study.
- Hepatorenal failure.
- Perioperative brain damage.
- Cardiovascular and/or respiratory failure requiring mechanical ventilation (> 2 days).
- Intraoperative complications
- Patients corresponding to the risk of anesthesia ASA III-IV.
- Refusal of relatives to participate in the study.

What is more important, all patients will be divided into 2 groups by the type of postoperative pain relief: 1-study group, 30 patients who during induction and throughout the entire period of surgery began intravenous infusion of dexmedetomidine at a dose of 1.0 mcg / kg / h against the background of planned maintenance of anesthesia with bolus administration of fentanyl in a dose of 10-20 mcg / kg, and low-flow inhalation of sevoflurane 0.4-1.5 vol%. 2-comparison group of 30 children who were anesthetized using the traditional method using fentanyl, propofol and sevoflurane against the background of planned maintenance of anesthesia with bolus administration of fentanyl in a dose of 10-20 mcg / kg, and low-flow inhalation of sevoflurane 0.4-1.5 vol%.

Results and their discussion. It should be suggested that based on the results of the study regarding the stabilization of the main parameters of hemodynamics and respiration confirms the adequacy of anesthetic protection in patients of group 1.

A decrease in heart rate, specific peripheral resistance and mean arterial pressure to 13% was recorded. In this group, the decrease in blood pressure and heart rate were hemodynamically insignificant. In addition, one can see the instability of the level of biochemical markers of pain glucose and cortisol at different stages of the examination.

According to BIS monitoring, the brain activity index was from 40 to 60, which indicates sufficient depth of sedation during anesthetic care.

In children of group 2, according to hemodynamics, a decrease in heart rate and mean blood pressure by 18% was observed, a moderate increase in lactate levels was recorded when exiting anesthesia. The brain activity index was from 45 to 70.

Conclusions. By summarizing it should be suggested that the specified method of anesthetic support with dexmedetomidine in combination with fentanyl and sevoflurane inhalation provides a sufficiently adequate level of sedation, effective analgesia and smooth flow of all components of anesthesia during open cardiac surgery in young children.

Figure №1 Results of the BIS monitoring study in children in the study groups

Thus, the mentioned method provides safe anesthesia, which is extremely important for postoperative mobilization and normalization of the patient after radical surgical interventions.

REFERENCES

1. Zozulya M.V., Lenkin A.I., Kurapeev I.S., Karelov A.E., Saiganov S.A., Lebedinsky K.M. Analgesia after cardiac surgery. *Anesthesiology and resuscitation*.2019;5:38-46. <https://doi.org/10.17116/anaesthesiology201905138>
2. Gregory J, McGowan L. An examination of the prevalence of acute pain for hospitalized adult patients: a systematic review. *J Clin Nurs*. 2016; 25 (5-6):583-98. doi:10.1111/jocn.13094.
3. Choinière M, Watt-Watson J, Victor JC. et al. Prevalence of and risk factors for persistent postoperative nonanginal pain after cardiac surgery: a 2-year prospective multicentre study. *CMAJ*. 2014;186(7):213-23. doi:10.1503/cmaj.131012.
4. Lauridsen MH, Kristensen AD, Hjortdal VE. et al. Chronic pain in children after cardiac surgery via sternotomy. *Cardiol Young*. 2014;24(5):893-9. doi:10.1017/S104795111300139X.
5. Gjeilo KH, Stenseth R, Wahba A, et al. Chronic postsurgical pain in patients 5 years after cardiac surgery: A prospective cohort study. *Eur J Pain*. 2017;21(3):425-33. doi: 10.1002/ejp.918
6. Kozlov I.A., Klypa T.V. Glucose-insulin mixture as a cardioprotector in cardiology and cardiac surgery. *General resuscitation*. 2017; 13(1): 57-72. DOI: 10.15360/1813-9779-2017-1-57-72.
7. Hausenloy D.J., Yellon D.M. Ischaemic conditioning and reperfusion injury. *Nat. Rev. Cardiol*. 2016; 13 (4): 193-209. DOI: 10.1038/nrcardio.2016.5. PMID: 26843289

8. Horak J., Mohler E.R., Fleisher L.A. Assessment of cardiac risk and the cardiology consultation. In: Kaplan J.A., Reich D.L., Savino J.S. (eds.). Kaplan's cardiac anesthesia: the echo era. 6th ed. St. Louis: Saunders; 2011: 2-15.
9. Sharma S., Durieux M.E. Molecular and genetic cardiovascular medicine. In: Kaplan J.A., Reich D.L., Savino J.S. (eds.). Kaplan's cardiac anesthesia: the echo era. 6th ed. St. Louis: Saunders; 2011: 157-177.
10. Grocott H.P., Stafford-Smith M., Mora-Mangano C.T. Cardiopulmonary bypass management and organ protection. In: Kaplan J.A., Reich D.L., Savino J.S. (eds.). Kaplan's cardiac anesthesia: the echo era. 6th ed. St. Louis: Saunders; 2011: 838-887.
11. Vinten-Johansen J., Thourani V.H. Myocardial protection: an overview. *J. Extra Corpor. Technol.* 2000; 32 (1): 38-48. PMID: 10947622
12. Kozlov I.A. Alpha 2-adrenergic receptor agonist dexmedetomidine in the practice of modern sedation. *General resuscitation.* 2013; 9(2):55-65. DOI: 10.15360/1813-9779-2013-2-55
13. Kozlov I.A. Dexmedetomidine in anesthesiology and resuscitation of cardiac surgery / *Cardiology and cardiovascular surgery.* 2014; 7(4):100-108.
14. Ji F., Li Z., Nguyen H., Young N., Shi P., Fleming N., Liu H. Perioperative dexmedetomidine improves outcomes of cardiac surgery. *Circulation.* 2013; 127 (15): 1576-1584. DOI: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONA-HA.112.000936. PMID: 23513068.
15. Zhang X., Zhao X., Wang Y. Dexmedetomidine: a review of applications for cardiac surgery during perioperative period. *J. Anesth.* 2015; 29 (1): 102-111. DOI: 10.1007/s00540-014-1857-z. PMID: 24913070.
16. Soliman R., Zohry G. The myocardial protective effect of dexmedetomidine in high-risk patients undergoing aortic vascular surgery. *Ann. Card. Anaesth.* 2016; 19 (4): 606-613. DOI: 10.4103/0971-9784.191570. PMID: 27716690.
17. Brandão P.G., Lobo F.R., Ramin S.L., Sakr Y., Machado M.N., Lobo S. M. Dexmedetomidine as an anesthetic adjuvant in cardiac surgery: a cohort study. *Braz. J. Cardiovasc. Surg.* 2016; 31 (3): 213-218. DOI: 10.5935/1678-9741.20160043. PMID: 27737403